

ENHANCING THERMAL AND FIRE RESISTANCE IN MULTILAYER LOW-CARBON BUILDING STRUCTURES: MATERIAL PERFORMANCE AND DESIGN OPTIMIZATION

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Abstract: This article provides a comprehensive analysis of thermal conductivity, thermal and fire resistance properties in buildings. Given the importance of effective insulation materials in the design and construction of modern buildings today, their temperature dynamics and thermal conductivity coefficients are evaluated and analyzed. In addition, each thermal resistance, application possibilities and fire resistance properties in multilayer structures are also considered. The main purpose of the article is to determine the effectiveness of materials used in multilayer structures and to improve their quality in building construction.

Keywords: Multilayer structures, thermal conductivity, thermal properties, fire resistance.

Currently, a wide range of measures are being implemented in the world to further deepen economic reforms in the building materials industry and accelerate the development of the industry, increase the production of new modern building materials, structures and products, and expand their types, and certain results are being achieved. Expanding the types of building materials produced, increasing the share of modern, convenient and high-quality products produced on the basis of the localization program, and, in turn, reducing imports, and further developing the industry remain urgent issues today.

Particular attention is paid to the development of new compositions of building materials, and the creation of new compositions of multifunctional additives based on technogenic waste for the production of building materials is one of the important tasks of research in this direction. The development of new compositions of multifunctional additives and highly effective building materials with their participation is of great importance in substantiating relevant scientific solutions in the following areas: creating new methods for the production of building products based on technogenic additives, using new compositions to obtain multifunctional building materials with the participation

of secondary raw materials, increasing the strength indicators of heat-resistant and refractory building materials, optimizing the composition of raw materials to obtain low-energy building materials, modernizing the production technologies of heat-resistant and refractory building materials, and using local, alternative sources of active mineral additives to increase their volume.

In our republic, comprehensive measures are being implemented to produce high-quality building materials, modernize the economy and create new production capacities aimed at ensuring the demand for them. The Development Strategy of New Uzbekistan for 2022–2026 sets the tasks of “developing production sectors, modernizing and diversifying the industry, applying low-energy-saving methods in practice, developing the industry of building materials with polymer content, and producing import-substituting and export-oriented products.” In this regard, scientific research aimed at developing new compositions of multifunctional additives based on technogenic waste in the production of building materials and new types of highly efficient building materials with their participation is of great importance.

Regarding the improvement of methods for increasing thermal and fire resistance properties in buildings, It serves to implement the tasks set out in the Resolutions of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. PQ-4198 dated February 20, 2019 “On measures for the radical improvement and comprehensive development of the building materials industry”, No. PQ-4335 dated May 25, 2019 “On additional measures for the accelerated development of the building materials industry”, No. PQ-4992 dated February 13, 2021 “On measures for further reform and financial soundness of chemical industry enterprises, development of the production of high-value-added chemical products” and No. PQ-99 dated January 24, 2022 “On measures for the creation of an effective system for the development of production and expansion of industrial cooperation in the republic”, as well as other regulatory legal acts related to the activities of this sector.

Today, the issue of extending the service life of buildings is gaining importance. Therefore, the thermal conductivity and fire resistance properties of their structures are extremely important in the design of buildings. Multi-layer structures are widely used to effectively solve these problems. This article analyzes the main properties of CSPs, and their thermal insulation, thermal stability and fire resistance aspects are studied[1-3].

Multi-layer barrier structures consist of different materials, each layer performing a different function. In general, CCPs consist of the following elements:

-The outer layer (external or internal): This layer is selected from aesthetic and weather-resistant materials.

-Insulation layer: This layer provides thermal insulation. Its main function is to reduce heat energy loss.

- CCP structures: These structures provide strength and distribute the overall load. The mechanical and physical properties of each layer are selected based on their construction purposes and are specifically designed to provide optimal strength.

Table 1.

Insulation in multilayer structures thermal conductivity coefficients of materials

Insulation material	Thermal conductivity coefficient (λ , W/m·K)	Floor value (d, m)	Thermal resistance (R, m ² ·K/W)
Aerogel	0.013	0.02	1.54
Styrofoam	0.035	0.02	0.57

Table 1 provides information on the thermal conductivity coefficients of insulation materials used in multilayer barrier structures. The table shows materials such as aerogel, foam plastic and mineral wool, and for each of them the thermal conductivity coefficient (λ), layer value (d) and thermal resistance (R) are indicated. This table will be the main source for determining the effectiveness of insulation materials and choosing the most appropriate options in construction.

In multilayer structures, thermal conductivity is determined by the thermal resistance of the materials. This indicator is estimated using R-values, the higher the R-value, the better the thermal insulation of the material. In the CSP, the thermal conductivity of each layer is taken into account separately, and due to their interaction, the overall thermal insulation is increased. For example, modern materials such as polystyrene or mineral wool insulation provide a high level of insulation. This contributes to energy efficiency and reduces the cost of heating buildings in winter. When thermal stability is high, it becomes possible to create a comfortable microclimate in the building. Temperature changes occur slowly, which creates comfort for residents [4-5].

Thermal stability is important for human comfort, and to ensure a comfortable microclimate in buildings, it is necessary to use thermosetting materials and structures [6-9]. That is, the thermal inertia of multilayer structures helps to prevent rapid temperature changes in the building. For example, in aerogel (Figure 1), the temperature dynamics are stable due to the slow transfer of heat in multilayer barrier structures. The presence of air or other insulating elements between the layers further increases thermal stability. This property is equally effective in summer and winter climatic conditions, reducing energy consumption in buildings.

Fig.1 . Temperature dynamics of an aerogel layered ETC

The fire resistance of multilayer structures depends on the degree of fire protection of the materials and their ability to maintain mechanical strength.

Table 2.

Thermal and fire resistance properties of multilayer barrier structures

Insulation material	Thermal properties	Fire resistance	Importance
Aerogel	High thermal efficiency	Harmonious, effective	Energy saving and environmental responsibility
Styrofoam	Average thermal efficiency	Harmonious, moderately productive	Cheap and effective when installed correctly

Table 2 provides information on the thermal and fire resistance properties of insulation materials in multilayer structures. The table shows the thermal

efficiency, fire resistance levels of materials such as aerogel, foam plastic and mineral wool and their importance in construction. The materials used in lightweight barrier structures (LFS) are classified according to their flammability properties and their fire resistance time is determined by F values. Non-combustible materials (for example, concrete or plaster) are used as the outer layer and help maintain the integrity of the structure for a long time in the event of a fire.

In conclusion, it should be said that multilayer structures have become an important factor in the construction of buildings, improving thermal insulation, ensuring thermal stability and increasing fire resistance. The use of modern materials and technologies further increases the efficiency of CSPs, which significantly contributes to the construction of energy-efficient buildings. In the future, further development and implementation of today's innovative solutions is important in terms of energy saving in the construction industry.

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